

Samples	Irritation score based on (Congestion, Blood hemorrhage Coagulation)	Irritation assessment
Sterile distilled water (Negative control)	0	Non-irritant
NaOH (0.1M) (Positive control)	18.82	Strong irritant
Cell Free Supernatant (CSF)		
24 th hour prometabolite (CFS)	0	Non-irritant
<3 Kda CFS fraction	0	Non-irritant
Pediocin (Sigma) S9	0	Non-irritant